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Volatilisation of minor and trace elements during cement clinker formation in a high CO₂ atmosphere

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Background

- The production of cement clinker is responsible for high CO₂ emissions
 - Fuel emissions
 - Process emissions due to $\text{CaCO}_3 \leftrightarrow \text{CaO} + \text{CO}_2$
- Carbon capture has emerged as an attractive mitigation technique
 - Direct capture is facilitated by high concentrations of CO₂ in the flue gas
- How does a high CO₂ process atmosphere affect the volatilization of minor and trace elements?

Materials and methods

- Two industrial cement raw meals exposed in two different atmospheres at 1450°C for 40 min
 - 95% CO₂ 5% O₂
 - 20% CO₂ 5% O₂ 10% H₂O 65% N₂
- Analyzed before and after exposure with ICP-SFMS for 68 different elements
- XRD to confirm clinker formation
- Multicomponent equilibrium calculations to help interpret results

	RM-A	RM-B
CaO (wt.-%)	44.91	46.45
SiO ₂ (wt.-%)	14.35	14.59
Al ₂ O ₃ (wt.-%)	3.48	3.97
Fe ₂ O ₃ (wt.-%)	1.92	1.86
MgO (wt.-%)	2.39	0.79
K ₂ O (wt.-%)	0.84	0.94
Na ₂ O (wt.-%)	0.18	0.084
TiO ₂ (wt.-%)	0.20	0.14
Mn ₂ O ₃ (wt.-%)	0.074	0.42
ZnO (wt.-%)	0.047	0.0029
P ₂ O ₅ (wt.-%)	0.030	0.094
SO ₃ (wt.-%)	1.09	0.28
LSF	98.62	99.38
SM	2.66	2.50
AM	1.81	2.13
LOI (wt.-%)	33.3	34.9

Results – major elements

Results – minor elements

Results – volatile trace elements elements

Results – non volatile trace elements

Multicomponent equilibrium calculations

- Elements included in the calculations were Al, C, Ca, Cl, Fe, K, Mg, Mn, Na, O, P, S, Si, Ti (and N for reference atmosphere)
- Using FactSage 8.4 over a temperature range of 600-1450 °C
- FactPS and FToxid, as well as a customized database for salt melt and alite solid solution were used [1,2]
- The solution phases: A-Slag liq, Bredigite, C-a'(Ca,Sr,Ba)₂SiO₄, B-a(Ca,Sr)₂SiO₄, A-Olivine, Ca₂(Al,Fe)₂O₅, Ca₃(Al,Fe)₂O₆, MX25-Salt, MX25-AlkH, MX25-Hexa, MX25-Fair and MX25-Glas

[1] D. Lindberg, R. Backman, P. Chartrand, and M. Hupa, "Towards a comprehensive thermodynamic database for ash-forming elements in biomass and waste combustion — Current situation and future developments," Fuel Processing Technology, vol. 105, pp. 129-141, 2013/01/01/2013, doi: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.fuproc.2011.08.008>.

[2] E. Vighh, "Modeling the influence of magnesium from alternative raw materials on the chemistry of Portland cement clinker," 2023.

Results – equilibrium calculations

Results

Results

- Na_2CO_3 (Salt)
- K_2CO_3 (Salt)
- CaCO_3 (Salt)
- Na_2CO_3 (Hexa)
- K_2CO_3 (Hexa)
- CaCO_3 (Hexa)
- $\text{K}_2\text{Ca}(\text{CO}_3)_2$ (Fair)
- $\text{Na}_2\text{Ca}(\text{CO}_3)_2$ (Fair)

Conclusion

- For both atmospheres the minor elements K and S, and the trace elements RB, Pb, Tl, Cs, Cd, Hg were highly volatile
- Overall lower volatilization in high CO₂ atmosphere
- Biggest difference between atmospheres for K, S (and Na)
- Change in volatilization for K, S and Na supported by calculations
 - A combination of hydroxide formation in ref atmosphere and increased carbonate formation in high CO₂ atmosphere

} Experimental

→ The effect of increased alkali and sulfur retention has on clinker quality should be studied

→ No clear hindrance from a trace element perspective to change process atmosphere to high CO₂

Thank you!

Questions?

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